

Crop Protection Strategies Against Wild Boar and Deer

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(A) Electrified fence with conductive wires at 20, 50 and 120 cm from the ground. (B) Individual protection in metal mesh. (Figure adapted from Di Luzio, 2011)

The increase in wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) and deer (*Cervus elaphus*) populations in the Bragança region has caused damage to agriculture, requiring specific strategies for each species. The unbalanced increase in populations is largely due to the scarcity of natural predators, such as the Iberian wolf (*Cannis lupus signatus*), which plays an essential role in ecological balance. The reduction in wolves, coupled with the abandonment of traditional land management practices, has created ideal conditions for the growth of wild boar and deer populations. To protect crops, wild boars require robust measures. Electric fencing, installed with wires at 20 and 50 cm from the ground, is the most effective method, as they prevent animals from passing through and discourage digging. The minimum recommended voltage is 3500 volts, accompanied by a frequent maintenance to ensure functionality. In addition, game management through selective hunting, especially of juveniles and females, is essential to control population growth. The recent relaxation of hunting by approaching and waiting during the full moon offers farmers and local managers an additional tool to reduce damage. In addition, it is possible to apply to the Institute for Nature Conservation and Forests for a specific authorisation to control the population. In the case of deer, trees and small horticultural crops can be protected with individual guards, such as metal nets or plastic cylinders of least 2 metres high. The protectors can be removed and replaced during critical periods. The strategies are different but complementary. While wild boar requires a population reduction, deer control should focus on restricting access to cultivated areas. In the long term, restoring the wolf's presence and promoting land management practices will be crucial to restoring the natural balance and safeguarding the region's agriculture.

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